

Some Aspects of Uptake of Cadmium by Calcium Hydroxylapatite and the Effect of Such Incorporation in the Solubility of Bone Mineral

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The uptake of cadmium by the synthetic hydroxylapatite is facilitated by increase in Cd^{2+} conc., a decrease in pH of medium of exchange and in the particle size of hydroxylapatite. Adsorption of Cd^{2+} and its accompanying diffusion into the interior of the crystals of hydroxylapatite explain the mechanism of exchange.

CALCIUM hydroxylapatite which is also called bone mineral (CaHA), $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$ is the major inorganic crystalline component of human skeletal system¹. It undergoes a series of cationic and anionic replacement reactions². $\text{Ca}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Cd}^{2+}$ replacement reaction in CaHA is of extreme biological significance as it explains the mechanism of incorporation of cadmium into human skeletal system according to the following equation

The incorporation of cadmium *in vivo* due to environmental pollution has acquired importance currently and hence the study of the uptake of cadmium by CaHA and the effect of such incorporation in the solubility of bone mineral has been investigated with synthetic samples and reported in this paper.

Experimental

Pure and homogeneous samples of CaHA for the study of the dependence of uptake of cadmium by CaHA and the samples of CaHA containing varying quantities of cadmium in the form of solid solution for the study of the effect of incorporation of cadmium in the solubility of bone mineral were prepared by co-precipitation—a method specially worked out for this purpose³. The chemical composition of these samples were determined^{4,5}.

The dependence of uptake of cadmium by CaHA on factors like pH in the physiologically important range of 5.0 to 8.0, concentration of Cd^{2+} ion in the range between 0.01M to 0.01M of $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and on particle size between 60 to 320 mesh μ and the kinetics of $\text{Ca}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Cd}^{2+}$ exchange on hydroxylapatite were investigated. 0.2 g of CaHA was equilibrated at physiologically important temperature of $37^\circ \pm .5^\circ$

with a solution of 100 ml of $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{AR})$ by shaking in air tight polythene containers mechanically changing the factors effecting the uptake investigation each time while other factors were kept constant. At the end of the desired period of equilibration the contents were filtered through a IG_4 crucible. The residue was washed with a doubly distilled water till it was free from the absorbed cadmium and the calcium and the cadmium content in the residue was determined⁴.

The effect of the incorporation of cadmium on the solubility of bone mineral was carried out as follows. The solubility studies were based exclusively on the micro analytical determination of phosphate⁵ in the

Fig. 1. Uptake of Cadmium by Calcium hydroxylapatite.

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solution of the samples after equilibration. Potassium acid phthalate—sodium hydroxide and veronal—HCl were used as buffer combinations. The pH was measured with a line operated Backman pH meter before and after equilibration to ascertain its constancy. 0.2 g of 220 mesh (B.S.S.) of each of the sample was added to 100 ml of the buffer solution prepared in carbon dioxide free double distilled water taken in air tight polythene containers which were shaken mechanically at a regulated speed at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ$ to simulate biological condition. At the desired period of equilibration the crystals were separately filtered through IG₄ crucible and the phosphate content in the filtrate was determined complexometrically.

Results and Discussion

Fig. 2. pH dependence of solubility of calcium-cadmium hydroxylapatite.

The results of uptake of cadmium by CaHA are represented diagrammatically in Fig. 1. The uptake of Cd²⁺ by CaHA was found to (i) decrease with increase of pH in the physiologically important range of 5.0 to 8.0 (Fig. 1A). (ii) Increases with increase of Cd²⁺ and increases with decreases in particle size of CaHA (Fig. 1B & 1C) respectively. The solubility studies of CaHA and CdHA indicate that the CdHA is less soluble than CaHA at a given pH (see Fig. 2A) as such CdHA is preferentially precipitated leading to the formation of Ca-CdHA according to the equation already suggested above. The exchange is found to be very rapid upto 2 hr and remains almost constant thereafter (Fig. 1). (The exchange varies linearly with conc. of Cd²⁺ from 13.5 to 25.60 wt% of CdHA for an increase

in the conc. of Cd(NO₃)₂ from 0.01 to 0.1M. It is also linear function of pH, from 25.6 to 32.58 wt% for decreasing in pH from 8.0 to 5.0. Fig. 1C shows that the exchange under a given set of experimental condition increases from 20.02 to 36.86 wt% for a decrease in mean radius of the particle (from 70 to 320μ). The fact that exchange increases with the decrease in particle size of CaHA (Fig. 1C) and with increase in Cd²⁺ conc. (Fig. 1B) leads to the supposition that the first rapid stage is surface dependent. The second stage of exchange may be diffusion controlled and hence slow. Similar observations were reported in case of Ca²⁺ Pb²⁺ exchange in CaHA.⁶

The results of incorporation of Cd²⁺ in the solubility of bone mineral was represented diagrammatically in Fig. 2. The dependence of solubility on (i) the pH of medium of equilibration over physiologically important range of 5.0 to 8.0 and (ii) the cadmium content in the sample at a given pH was investigated. It was observed that (i) the solubility of a given sample decreases with increase of pH of dissolving medium of (PO₄³⁻) ion in the dissolving medium⁷ and (ii) at a given pH the solubility decreased initially and increased after 20 mole of cadmium hydroxylapatite and the solid solution (Fig. 2B). This observation can be explained on the basis of (i) the common ion effect applied to solubility products according to Furedi Milhofer⁸ and to the formation of some covalent bonds on introduction of Cd²⁺ in CaHA⁹. This explains the role of incorporation of Cd²⁺ in the solubility behaviour of the bone mineral.

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